

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
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“The Essence Remains the Same: Generative Modeling of Expressive Percussion”

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation and Research Question

1.1.1 Research Question

This thesis focuses on using generative models for capturing the expressiveness in percussion music, the nuances that make human performances unique and engaging, also known as groove. Groove is a natural part of human musical performance. It encompasses the subtle timing deviations, dynamics, and articulations that make a performance feel alive and engaging. As a central aspect of music perception and appreciation, it is closely connected to the main functional uses of music; namely, dance, drill, and ritual. When seeking to find a relationship between music and the behavior that groove induces, synchronization and coordination, the temporal properties of the music signal are crucial to our understanding of groove. [Davies et al., 2013]

Generative models have shown great promise in various creative domains, including music generation. They can learn from existing performances and generate new, expressive musical content. They can also learn to mimic specific styles or techniques, allowing for greater control and customization.

Percussion music, in particular, offers a rich landscape for exploring expressivity. The nuances in timing, dynamics, and articulation are crucial for conveying the intended feel and groove of a piece. Percussion instruments, with their diverse timbres and playing techniques, present unique challenges and opportunities for generative modeling. The rich variety of sounds and rhythms in percussion music can be difficult to capture and reproduce accurately, but they also provide a wealth of material for training generative models. This diversity is what makes percussion music so compelling, and it is essential to develop methods that can effectively model and generate these intricate patterns.

My research focuses on leveraging generative models to capture the nuances of per-

cussion and enhance its expressivity.

1.1.2 Motivation

The motivation behind this research lies in the desire to bridge the gap between human expressivity and machine-generated music. By understanding and modeling the nuances of percussion performance, we can create systems that not only generate music but also enhance the creative process for musicians. This has the potential to revolutionize the way we compose, perform, and interact with music technology.

While generative models have made significant strides in music generation quality, there is still a gap in the ways we can interact with these systems. Text input methods, while great for high-level descriptions, cannot be used to effectively describe the temporal evolution at a fine granularity. Talking about music often involves discussing its structure, harmony, and melody, but the subtleties of rhythm and timing are more challenging to convey through text alone. Talking about music also requires a shared understanding of its cultural and contextual nuances, which can be difficult to articulate.

Music generation systems today are trained on large paired datasets of text and music, but these datasets often lack the depth needed to capture the intricacies of percussion performance. Moreover, the unique characteristics of percussion instruments, such as their diverse timbres and playing techniques, are often underrepresented in these datasets. This underrepresentation can lead to generative models that lack the ability to produce authentic and expressive percussion music.

Another motivation is the desire to make these tools more accessible to a wider range of musicians and producers. A large number of these models are trained and deployed on cloud infrastructure, which can be a barrier for many users due to cost, latency, and privacy concerns. Music generation systems that can run efficiently on local hardware would enable more spontaneous and intimate music-making experiences. In addition, if the system can be adapted to the specific musical context and preferences of the user, it could lead to more personalized and meaningful musical experiences.

1.2 Objectives and Contributions

1.2.1 Objectives

This research employs a multi-faceted approach to address the challenges identified in the previous sections.

1. Rhythms can be described to the model the way people naturally communicate about them, using a combination of verbal descriptions, visual notations, and audio examples. Verbal descriptions can include terms like "syncopation," "polyrhythm," and "groove," while visual notations can involve standard drum

tabs, or custom piano roll representations. Audio examples can help convey the desired feel and style of the rhythm. These descriptions can provide better temporal context and timbral information compared to text alone.

2. The model can natively run on local hardware, such as a laptop without a dedicated GPU, using platform independent serialized models with efficient architectures. This would allow for real-time interaction and feedback, enabling musicians to experiment and iterate on their ideas more freely.
3. The model should have an easy-to-use interface, allowing musicians to interact with it intuitively and creatively.
4. The model should be easily fine-tuned, enabling users to adapt it to their unique musical repertoire and preferences.

1.2.2 Contributions

- Expressive groove modeling and generation in symbolic representations of percussion music - A general framework for learning groove from symbolic percussion datasets with expressive timing and dynamics. I designed a model architecture that can effectively capture the nuances of human percussion performances, including timing deviations and dynamic variations. This model can be used to add expressive information to quantized drum patterns, or for modifying groove style of existing patterns. This work was published at the ICMC 2025 conference under the name "Learning Microrhythm in Uruguayan Candombe using Transformers". [Mishra et al., 2025]
- Audio percussion generation with fine-grained temporal and timbral control - A system for generating audio percussion loops with precise control over timing and timbre. This involves the use of latent diffusion models conditioned on timbre info and temporal rhythmic control to create realistic and expressive percussion sounds. This work is currently being prepared for publication.
- Plugins for real-time use in digital audio workstations (DAWs) - Developed plugins that integrate the generative models directly into VSTs, enabling musicians to generate and manipulate expressive percussion patterns interactively in DAWs. This allows for seamless integration into existing music production workflows, making it easier for musicians to experiment with and utilize the generative models in their creative processes. This work was published in the Extended Abstracts of the ISMIR 2024 conference under the name "Groove Transformer VST for Latin American Rhythms". [Mishra et al., 2024] A talk was also presented at the ADCx India 2025 conference.

1.3 Structure of the Thesis

The structure of this thesis is organized into five chapters. Each chapter addresses different aspects of the research problem and contributes to the overall objectives

outlined earlier. An overview of the contents of the following chapters is provided below.

Chapter 2: Learning Microrhythm in Uruguayan Candombe using Transformers This chapter presents a model architecture that captures the nuances of human percussion performances, including timing deviations and dynamic variations. The model is designed to add expressive information to quantized drum patterns or modify the groove style of existing patterns. The chapter discusses the dataset used, the training process, and the evaluation metrics. The results demonstrate the model's ability to generate expressive percussion patterns that closely resemble human performances.

Chapter 3: GotThatFlow: Flow-based Beatbox-to-Rhythm Generation This chapter introduces a novel approach for generating drum patterns from beatbox input using flow-based generative models. The proposed method leverages the temporal structure of beatbox performances to create corresponding drum patterns, effectively translating vocal rhythms into instrumental grooves. The chapter details the model architecture, training procedure, and evaluation framework, highlighting the system's ability to produce high-quality rhythmic outputs that maintain the expressiveness of the original beatbox input.

Chapter 4: Model Deployment for End Users

This chapter focuses on the practical aspects of deploying the developed models and integrating them into existing music production workflows. The chapter covers the implementation of user-friendly interfaces and real-time performance considerations, ensuring that musicians can easily access and utilize the generative capabilities of the models in their creative processes.

Chapter 5: Conclusion and Future Work This chapter summarizes the key findings of the thesis and discusses their implications for the field of music technology. It also outlines potential directions for future research, including the exploration of new model architectures, the incorporation of additional musical styles, and the development of more sophisticated evaluation methods for generative systems.

Chapter 2

Learning Microrhythm in Uruguayan Candombe using Transformers

In this chapter, I discuss the application of transformer models to learn and generate microrhythms from Uruguayan Candombe music. This chapter builds upon work that was previously presented at the ICMC 2025 conference [Mishra et al., 2025]. I was responsible for leading the project, and it was undertaken together with Satyajeeet Prabhu, Behzad Haki, and Martin Rocamora. Throughout the text, the pronoun "we" is used to acknowledge this collaborative effort, while reflecting my role in leading this work.

2.1 Abstract

Musical performance is shaped not only by the notes that are played, but also by subtle deviations in their timing and intensity. These microrhythms—fine-grained variations in onset placement, dynamics, and other expressive parameters—are central to creating the sense of groove and feel in live performance. In contrast, electronic music production environments often attempt to emulate these qualities through quantization adjustments or rule-based humanization algorithms, which typically fall short of capturing the depth and cultural specificity of real performance practice.

In this work, we investigate the generation of expressive drum patterns by directly learning microtiming and dynamic nuances from annotated performances. Specifically, we model microrhythm as a sequence learning problem and employ a Transformer-based architecture to capture temporal dependencies across beats and cycles. Our case study centers on Uruguayan candombe drumming, whose complex rhythmic structures provide a rich domain for exploring expressive timing at both the beat level and across full rhythmic cycles.

To assess the extent to which the model can reproduce the stylistic characteristics of human performance, we compare generated outputs against the original annotations using statistical measures such as the mean and standard deviation of timing

deviations, as well as histogram intersection for both timing and dynamic values at each subdivision.

Through this study, our broader aim is to narrow the gap between algorithmic rhythm generation and the expressive qualities of live musicianship. By capturing the microstructural elements of groove, we seek to create generative systems that can reproduce the rhythmic feel of culturally grounded traditions such as Latin American drumming, thereby enabling more authentic and musically compelling applications in electronic composition and production.

2.2 Introduction

Microtiming refers to subtle deviations from strict, grid-based timing in musical performance, where notes are played slightly ahead of or behind their expected metrical positions. These fine-grained variations, often accompanied by nuances in dynamics and articulation, contribute significantly to the expressive quality of a performance and are central to the perception of groove [Davies et al., 2013]. More broadly, the term microrhythm has recently been proposed to encompass these timing deviations alongside other rhythmic nuances that shape the listener’s sense of feel [Danielsen et al., 2024].

Our focus in this work is candombe drumming, a central element of Uruguayan popular culture [Ferreira, 2007]. Candombe is performed using three distinct drums—*chico*, *repique*, and *piano*—each of which plays a characteristic rhythmic role. In addition, all three drums share the *madera* or *clave* timeline pattern, whose function parallels that of guiding rhythmic structures in Afro-Cuban and sub-Saharan African traditions. The overall candombe groove emerges from the interplay of these layered patterns, which unfold within a four-beat metric cycle subdivided into sixteen pulses [Sethares, 2014, Jure and Rocamora, 2018]. Previous studies have analyzed the microtiming properties of candombe, demonstrating its distinctive rhythmic feel and structural complexity [Jure and Rocamora, 2016, Fuentes et al., 2019, Jure and Rocamora, 2018].

While traditional Western notation has difficulty capturing such expressive timing nuances, Digital Audio Workstations (DAWs) provide tools for manipulating timing directly. Most DAWs, however, operate on rigid quantized grids and approximate expressive performance using pre-defined functions such as swing or humanization. These typically apply fixed deviations at certain subdivisions, producing consistent but ultimately mechanical timing shifts that fail to capture the spontaneity and cultural specificity of live performance.

In this work, we focus on modeling microrhythm in Uruguayan candombe. We frame the task as sequence learning and employ a Transformer-based model trained on onset timing and strength annotations from real performances. To evaluate the model’s ability to reproduce stylistically accurate microtiming, we compare generated sequences with the original data using measures such as mean and standard

deviation of timing deviations, as well as histogram intersection for both timing and dynamics. Through this study, our goal is to build generative models that not only replicate the technical structure of candombe rhythms, but also embody their expressive groove, thereby contributing to the broader challenge of bridging algorithmic rhythm generation with the feel of live performance.

2.3 Related Work

Research on microtiming spans analytical studies of performance practice, symbolic representations of rhythm, and machine learning approaches for generative modeling.

2.3.1 Analytical studies of microtiming

Microtiming has been investigated across diverse musical traditions, often to characterize systematic deviations from the metrical grid. In jazz, for example, swing ratios have been measured as long-short patterns in consecutive eighth notes [Friberg and Sundström, 2002], while Irish fiddle music exhibits timing deviations at the eighth-note level [Rosinach and Caroline, 2006]. The Viennese Waltz demonstrates systematic variation at the quarter-note level, with the third beat in each bar shortened [Gabrielsson, 1985]. Iyer et al. [Iyer, 2002] further describe microrhythmic techniques within African-American music, linking them to embodied and cultural practices.

In Afro-Latin American traditions, microtiming has been shown to be essential for creating idiomatic groove. Davies et al. [Davies et al., 2013] synthesize samba patterns with microtiming deviations to study their perceptual effect, while Naveda et al. [Naveda et al., 2011] investigate how microtiming in samba interacts with dynamics, meter, and timbre. More broadly, Bilmes [Bilmes, 1993] introduced the concept of the tatum layer—the fastest regular pulse level of a meter—emphasizing that deviations at this level (i.e., microtiming shifts between performed events and their quantized positions) are central to rhythmic perception.

2.3.2 Symbolic and audio-based representations

Much of the analytical and computational literature relies on symbolic representations of rhythm, such as musical scores or MIDI sequences. These facilitate the study of microtiming as a structured series of event shifts occurring at a constant tempo [Bilmes, 1993]. At the symbolic level, microtiming is typically defined as the difference between the performed onset of a note and its idealized quantized grid position. However, datasets of symbolic scores are scarce for many non-Western and Latin American genres, prompting researchers to turn to audio recordings. In such cases, microtiming analyses rely on annotated onset and beat times, either obtained manually or through beat-tracking algorithms, which can then be converted to symbolic-like representations for systematic study.

2.3.3 Computational modeling and generation

Traditional methods for simulating microtiming in Digital Audio Workstations (DAWs) use parametric distributions. For example, Gaussian distributions may be fit to each sixteenth-note subdivision, and deviations are sampled randomly to “humanize” otherwise quantized patterns [Hennig et al., 2011]. While effective for adding variability, such methods lack the responsiveness and stylistic specificity of live performance.

Recent approaches increasingly frame microtiming generation as a sequence modeling problem. Graphical models have been applied to capture statistical dependencies across events [Fuentes et al., 2019], while sequence-to-sequence models [Gillick et al., 2019] and recurrent neural networks [Burloiu, 2020, Lee et al., 2021] have been used to predict onset deviations directly from symbolic input. More recently, Transformer architectures [Vaswani et al., 2017], originally developed for natural language processing, have been adopted for musical tasks, including drum sequence generation [Haki et al., 2022]. However, most existing datasets for these approaches remain heavily skewed toward rock and pop, limiting the generalizability of their learned groove representations.

Overall, prior work highlights both the universality of microtiming across traditions and the limitations of existing computational models. Analytical studies have shown how genre-specific timing practices shape groove, while computational work has proposed increasingly sophisticated models but has relied on datasets that underrepresent Afro-Latin American styles. Building on this foundation, the present work contributes by focusing on candombe drumming, employing Transformer-based sequence models to capture the culturally specific microrhythmic features of this tradition.

2.4 Dataset

The models presented in this work were trained on a candombe dataset derived from Rocamora et al. [Rocamora et al., 2015], collected as part of the Interpersonal Entrainment in Music Performance (IEMP) Project [Clayton et al., 2020]. Candombe is an Afro-Uruguayan percussive ensemble tradition whose cyclic, clave-based rhythm is central to Uruguayan popular culture. Recognized by UNESCO in 2009 as an Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity, candombe exhibits complex interlocking rhythms played on three principal drums: chico, repique, and piano. While a minimal ensemble comprises one of each drum, larger formations are common, and the tradition extends to street performances called *llamadas de tambores*, often involving dozens of drummers. The dataset analyzed here captures a more controlled studio setting with recordings from a total of five performers.

2.4.1 IEMP Candombe Dataset

The corpus consists of 12 performances: nine trios and three quartets. Trio performances feature three channels corresponding to the chico (C), piano (P), and repique 1 (R1) drums. Quartet recordings include an additional repique 2 (R2) channel. For modeling purposes, the quartets were reduced to three channels by discarding the R2 drum, allowing a uniform representation across all performances while preserving the essential rhythmic interactions of the ensemble. Each recording varies in duration, ranging approximately from 150 to 228 seconds per performance.

The dataset provides rich temporal and dynamic annotations. Metre annotations are based on manually tapping the first beat of each cycle, establishing the location of downbeats and the overall cycle structure. Onset annotations are available at the level of sixteenth-note subdivisions, including both the precise onset time in seconds and peak amplitude for each instrument. Additional metadata specifies which repique channel is playing the clave versus the repique pattern, event density over the preceding two seconds, and performer identities. This structured information enables detailed analyses of both timing and dynamic interactions between ensemble members.

To extract microtiming information, we first construct an isochronous grid for each rhythmic cycle, aligned to the manually tapped downbeats. For each annotated onset, the deviation from the corresponding sixteenth-note subdivision is computed, yielding the microtiming offsets that form the target for learning. Peak amplitude values provide a measure of expressive dynamics and are used in parallel with timing deviations to model the nuanced performance characteristics of each drum. By combining onset timing, dynamics, and ensemble configuration, this dataset allows the models to learn both the temporal and expressive structure of candombe drumming.

2.4.2 HVO representation

Data	Matrix	Values
Hits	$H_{32 \times 3}$	$h_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$
Velocities	$V_{32 \times 3}$	$v_{ij} \in [0, 1]$
Offsets	$O_{32 \times 3}$	$v_{ij} \in [-0.5, 0.5)$

Table 1: Input/output sequence representation for 2-bar beats in 4/4 with 16th note resolution for a total of 32 time steps (i), and 3 drum voices (j).

Following prior work [Gillick et al., 2019, Haki et al., 2022], we represent the annotated candombe performances using the HVO (HitsVelocitiesOffsets) matrix representation, which has proven effective for capturing expressive percussion performance in machine learning models. This representation separates the key dimensions of performance: hits, indicating whether a drum is struck at a particular time step; velocities, encoding the relative strength or loudness of each hit; and offsets, representing the microtiming deviation of each onset from the underlying metrical grid.

By decoupling these aspects, the model can learn not only the rhythmic structure but also the subtle expressive variations that characterize human performances.

Each performance is converted into three matrices of size $T \times M$, where T corresponds to the number of time steps and M to the number of drum channels. In our work, each time step corresponds to a sixteenth-note subdivision, and each matrix has three channels corresponding to chico, piano, and repique (R1, with R2 discarded for quartets). The hits matrix is obtained by quantizing the annotated onset times to the nearest sixteenth-note subdivision, assigning a value of 1 when a note is present and 0 otherwise. The offsets matrix captures the microtiming deviations, normalized to lie between -0.5 and 0.5 relative to a sixteenth-note duration, with negative values indicating anticipations and positive values delays. The velocities matrix encodes the strength of each hit, scaled linearly between 0 and 1 based on the peak amplitude of the onset annotations.

Based on prior work [Gillick et al., 2019], we segment the performances into overlapping two-bar sequences, with a stride of one bar between consecutive segments. Given that each bar contains 16 sixteenth-note subdivisions, each HVO sequence has a length of $T = 32$ time steps. This overlapping segmentation ensures that the model can learn dependencies across bar boundaries while also increasing the total number of training samples. Across the 12 recorded performances, this procedure yields a total of 1,070 two-bar sequences, which form the ground truth dataset for training and evaluation. A summary of the HVO representation is provided in Table 1.

2.5 Method

We approach the problem of modeling expressive drum performances as a *sequence-to-sequence prediction task*. Given a binary *hits matrix* indicating the presence or absence of hits across multiple drum channels over time, our goal is to predict both the *velocity* and *micro-timing offset* for each hit. By framing it this way, we can capture the temporal structure and inter-channel interactions that define a drum performance’s *micro-rhythmic feel*.

To accomplish this, we employ a transformer encoder that takes the hits matrix as input and outputs velocity and offset matrices of the same shape. The architecture is based on the encoder of the transformer from [Vaswani et al., 2017], and is illustrated in Figure 1. We process drum patterns over $T = 32$ time steps, encoding the hit patterns into expressive performance outputs. The encoder uses multi-head self-attention with 4 heads and a model dimension of 128. Feed-forward layers also have dimension 128, and the network consists of 11 stacked encoder blocks. We opt for a *transformer encoder* rather than a full encoder-decoder because the task involves predicting aligned sequences: each input hit corresponds directly to an output velocity and offset. The self-attention mechanism enables the model to capture both local and long-range temporal dependencies, as well as cross-channel interactions, which are crucial for modeling nuanced microtiming and groove.

Figure 1: Model architecture

The model jointly predicts velocities (\hat{V}) and timing offsets (\hat{O}). At each time step t , the output is split into two branches, both using \tanh activations: one for velocity \hat{v}_t and one for offset \hat{o}_t . Ground truth velocities and offsets (V, O) are scaled to $(-1, 1)$ to match the output range of \tanh . A square error loss is computed at each time step t for drum channel k as follows:

$$L_{t,k} = (v_{t,k} - \hat{v}_{t,k})^2 + (o_{t,k} - \hat{o}_{t,k})^2.$$

and mean is computed across all time steps and channels to obtain the final loss. To handle the sparsity of drum hits, we apply the hits matrix as a mask during loss computation, ensuring that only positions with actual hits contribute to the error. The network is trained end-to-end using teacher forcing, and parameters are updated with the Adam optimizer.

We found that \tanh activations provide better performance than sigmoid, as their range $(-1, 1)$ is zero-centered, unlike sigmoid's $(0, 1)$, which helps optimization by

reducing bias in the activations.

2.6 Experiments

For a qualitative evaluation of the microrhythms learned by our model, we focus on the musicological structure of candombe drumming. We select a single representative performance from the dataset, which includes multiple drums-Chico, Repique, and Piano-and extract its onset data at a resolution of sixteenth-note subdivisions. From these onsets, we infer velocities and timing offsets using our trained model. Candombe drumming exhibits repeating rhythmic structures at two distinct temporal levels: the beat and the full rhythmic cycle. We analyze the model’s inferences at both scales, evaluating its ability to reproduce the characteristic rhythmic patterns of the original performance.

2.6.1 Distribution of Chico onsets in beat

In candombe, the *chico* assumes the role of the timekeeper, playing repeating patterns at the level of the beat throughout the entire performance (see Figure 2) [Fuentes et al., 2019]. To evaluate whether our model can capture its characteristic microtiming, we compare the distributions of chico onsets at the beat level between the actual performances and the model’s predictions. For this analysis, we employ the `carat` Python package [Jure and Rocamora, 2019], which allows precise examination of timing deviations across metric subdivisions.

Figure 3 shows the distribution of chico onsets for both actual (green) and predicted (red) data at the beat level. Each beat is divided into four sixteenth-note subdivisions, labeled as .1, .2, .3, and .4. We compute the mean offsets at each subdivision as a percentage of the beat duration, providing an intuitive representation of the average microtiming deviations relative to the isochronous metric grid. The results indicate that the model successfully captures the characteristic timing deviations of the chico, reproducing the subtle micro-rhythmic articulations present in the original performance.

Table 2 summarizes the mean, standard deviation, and histogram intersection values for each subdivision across the dataset, demonstrating that the predicted onset distributions closely match the ground truth. This confirms that the model effectively learns microtiming patterns unique to the chico, consistent with prior studies on candombe microtiming [Jure and Rocamora, 2016, 2019, Fuentes et al., 2019].

Accents play a central role in expressing groove [Danielsen et al., 2024], and since our model also predicts velocity, we compare actual and predicted velocity distributions at each beat subdivision. Figure 4 illustrates that the model captures the velocity trends observed in the ground truth. Notably, there is a discrepancy between the ground truth velocities and the theoretical pattern depicted in Figure 2, where an accent on the second subdivision is expected but not consistently reflected in the data. This highlights an interesting aspect of expressive performance that may

warrant further investigation.

Figure 2: Chico pattern of the performance shown in Figure 3 in music notation (the lower line represents the hand, and the upper line represents the stick). The pattern is repeated for each of the four beats of the rhythmic cycle.

Figure 3: Chico actual (top) vs predicted onsets (bottom) for all beats in one of the performances of the dataset.

2.6.2 Distribution of microtiming in cycle

We extend our analysis to examine microtiming trends across the duration of the full rhythmic cycle. First, we compute the mean, standard deviation, and histogram intersection of the distributions captured by the model for the chico drum against the ground truth distributions for all subdivisions within the cycle. As shown in Table 3, the distributions repeat every four subdivisions (i.e., every beat), consistent with the beat-level analysis, confirming that the chico pattern is preserved across the cycle.

Next, we focus on the *madera* pattern, which spans the full rhythmic cycle, as illus-

Figure 4: Predicted and actual velocities of chico onsets for all beats of the same performance of Figure 3.

Sub Div	Mean		Std		Hist Int
	Actual	Pred.	Actual	Pred.	
.1	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.84
.2	0.25	0.26	0.03	0.03	0.94
.3	0.48	0.49	0.02	0.02	0.81
.4	0.72	0.73	0.02	0.02	0.84

Table 2: Chico actual and predicted mean, standard deviation and histogram intersection of offset distribution across beats computed for the entire dataset.

trated in Figure 6. This pattern is initially played by all drums as an introduction and preparation for the rhythm, but during the main performance it is performed solely by the *repique* drum between phrases [Jure and Rocamora, 2016]. The IEMP candombe dataset provides annotations for sections containing the madera pattern. For this analysis, we consider the same performance used in Section 2.6.1, but focus on the cycles where the repique plays the madera pattern.

We analyze 59 cycles of repique madera hits to evaluate whether the model captures cycle-level microtiming patterns. Figure 5 displays the distribution of repique onsets for both the ground truth and the model’s predictions. The model successfully reproduces the characteristic microtiming of the madera pattern. Notably, the onsets at the 4th subdivision of the first and fourth beats (1.4 and 4.4) occur slightly ahead of the isochronous grid, consistent with the expressive deviations observed in the original performance. This demonstrates that our model can learn and replicate not only beat-level timing but also subtler microtiming patterns that emerge across the full rhythmic cycle.

Figure 5: Example of madera patterns actual vs predicted onsets

Figure 6: The two *madera* patterns played by the repique drum in the performance of Figure 5, shown in music notation (\times symbol indicates a madera hit). The performance starts with the top pattern and then transitions to the bottom pattern.

2.7 Discussion

In this work, we investigated the problem of learning microrhythmic characteristics in Uruguayan candombe drumming. We represented onset timing and strength data as *hits*, *velocity*, and *offset* (HVO) matrices and trained a transformer model on sequences of 2-bar length. After training, the model was used to infer velocities and timing offsets from hit information, allowing us to evaluate its performance at multiple temporal scales.

Our qualitative analysis focused on two levels of rhythmic structure: the *beat* level, using the Chico drum as the timekeeper, and the *cycle* level, using the Madera pattern played by the Repique drum. At the beat level, we observed that the model accurately captured the microtiming deviations of the Chico drum, reproducing both

Sub Div	Mean		Std		Hist Int
	<i>Actual</i>	<i>Pred.</i>	<i>Actual</i>	<i>Pred.</i>	
1.1	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.71
1.2	0.26	0.26	0.03	0.03	0.83
1.3	0.49	0.49	0.02	0.02	0.65
1.4	0.73	0.73	0.02	0.02	0.84
2.1	1.01	1.01	0.02	0.02	0.79
2.2	1.25	1.25	0.03	0.03	0.85
2.3	1.48	1.48	0.02	0.02	0.84
2.4	1.73	1.73	0.02	0.02	0.86
3.1	2.01	2.01	0.02	0.02	0.81
3.2	2.25	2.25	0.03	0.03	0.84
3.3	2.48	2.48	0.02	0.02	0.83
3.4	2.72	2.72	0.02	0.02	0.74
4.1	3.01	3.01	0.02	0.02	0.79
4.2	3.26	3.26	0.03	0.03	0.82
4.3	3.48	3.49	0.02	0.02	0.86
4.4	3.72	3.73	0.02	0.02	0.84

Table 3: Chico actual and predicted mean, standard deviation and histogram intersection of offset distribution across rhythmic cycles computed for the entire dataset.

the mean and standard deviation of the original distributions. Additionally, the predicted velocity profiles closely matched those of the ground truth, demonstrating that the model is capable of learning not only the timing but also the dynamic accents that contribute to groove in candombe.

At the cycle level, the Chico microtiming patterns were preserved across the full rhythmic cycle, reflecting the timekeeper behavior of this instrument. Furthermore, the model successfully reproduced the microtiming of the Madera pattern played by the Repique drum, capturing subtle deviations such as the anticipatory onsets on the 4th subdivision of specific beats. These results demonstrate that the model is capable of learning complex, hierarchical rhythmic structures and expressive timing across multiple temporal scales.

2.8 Conclusion and Future Work

The transformer architecture used in this study proves effective for learning microtiming patterns from HVO representations, suggesting that the approach is generalizable to other datasets and musical genres. By capturing both timing and velocity distributions, our model provides a tool for analyzing, generating, and manipulating rhythmic microstructure in a data-driven manner. This has potential applications in algorithmic rhythm creation, music production, and the study of performance practice across different musical traditions.

In conclusion, our work demonstrates that deep learning models can successfully learn the microrhythmic structure of complex rhythmic traditions such as candombe. The model reproduces both timing deviations and dynamic accents at multiple temporal levels, highlighting the capability of data-driven approaches to capture expressive performance characteristics. Future work will focus on extending this methodology to other Latin American music genres, contributing to the development of more versatile tools for rhythm modeling and creative music applications.

Chapter 3

GotThatFlow: Flow-based Beatbox-to-Drum Generation

In this chapter, I present the application of diffusion models for generating drum audio conditioned on rhythmic inputs such as beatboxing or tapping. This work has been carried out in collaboration with Patrick O’Reilly and Hugo Flores Garcia from the Interactive Audio Lab at Northwestern University. I have led the implementation of the code and the execution of the experiments, while benefiting greatly from the insightful guidance and suggestions provided by Patrick and Hugo in shaping the methodology and refining the experimental procedures.

Throughout the chapter, the pronoun “we” is used to acknowledge this collaborative effort while reflecting my role in leading this work.

3.1 Abstract

Musicians frequently rely on intuitive rhythmic gestures, such as tapping or beatboxing, to communicate drum patterns. While these vocal or percussive sketches convey hits and timing effectively, converting them into high quality drum tracks often requires substantial manual effort. To address this, we present GotThatFlow, a flow based generative model that maps raw rhythmic gestures to realistic drum recordings. GotThatFlow is developed over the Stable Audio Open Small model which is fine tuned following the Sketch2Sound paradigm. The model is conditioned using a combination of prepend conditioning and cross conditioning, enabling it to capture both timbral structure and rhythmic variation. Users can supply one audio input that encodes the rhythm (e.g., a beatboxing track) and another that specifies the target drumkit timbre. The result is a system capable of producing rhythmically coherent drum performances from unseen timbres in a zero shot manner.

3.2 Introduction

Rhythmic gestures such as tapping or beatboxing serve as a natural shorthand for communicating drum patterns. These forms of expression rarely correspond to a literal transcription of a full drum arrangement; instead, they often encode a compressed, higher level representation of rhythmic intent. For example, a beatboxer might simplify complex textures by voicing only one component of a simultaneous onset, or omit certain strokes altogether while leaving them implied. Turning these sketches into polished drum productions typically involves a long chain of steps: mapping voiced sounds to specific drumkit elements, reconstructing missing or implied events, arranging and sequencing the performance, and finally applying synthesis or recording alongside additional timbral shaping. Such a process can be both time consuming and disruptive to fast paced creative workflows. To streamline this, we introduce GotThatFlow, a flow based generative model designed to transform arbitrary rhythmic sound gestures directly into realistic, full drumkit audio. The system operates from two audio prompts: one capturing the rhythmic structure through a sound gesture (e.g., beatboxing) and another specifying the target timbre via an example drum recording. By leveraging both prepend and cross conditioning, GotThatFlow synthesizes complete drum arrangements that elaborate on the input rhythm while faithfully matching the desired timbre. Despite being trained on less than 10 hours of purely drum stems (MusDB18-HQ [Rafii et al., 2017]) and comprising only 347M trainable parameters, GotThatFlow produces temporally aligned realizations from previously unseen timbres under zero shot conditions.

3.3 Related Work

The expansion of simple rhythmic inputs into full drum arrangements has been extensively studied in the symbolic domain. A prominent example is the GrooVAE framework by Gillick et al. [Gillick et al., 2019], which transforms single channel MIDI drum patterns into expressive, multi voice MIDI performances. However, these symbolic models do not address conditioning on audio gestures or timbral examples, limiting their applicability for direct audio-to-audio translation.

In the audio domain, Santos and Cardoso investigated tap-to-drums translation using the RAVE model [Caillon and Esling, 2021, Santos and Cardoso, 2023]. While RAVE effectively maps rhythmic gestures to drum audio, it requires retraining for each new target timbre, making it impractical for zero-shot timbre specification via audio conditioning. More generally, neural timbre transfer systems in the audio domain often share this limitation, or are designed primarily for pitched instruments rather than drums [Engel et al., 2019, Demerlé et al., 2024]. These constraints highlight the need for systems capable of flexible, zero-shot audio-conditioned drum generation.

Another family of approaches relies on transcription-based pipelines, where beatboxing is transcribed into symbolic drum events and then synthesized into audio [Ramires et al., 2018]. These systems typically depend on user-specific calibration

to achieve accurate transcription and remain limited to well-defined mappings between gestures and drum timbres. As a result, they struggle to generalize to more diverse input types and are often confined to literal, one-to-one mappings of sound events.

In contrast, our work introduces a self-supervised, audio-prompted method that directly generates full drumkit recordings from rhythmic gestures, without relying on symbolic transcription. This enables the model to infer and elaborate on arrangement details that may be implied but not explicitly present in the input. Our system extracts TRIA [O’Reilly et al.] features directly from non-drum sound inputs (e.g., tapping or beatboxing) and uses them to guide the generation of drum performances.

Finally, our contribution differs from earlier work on symbolic rhythm generation [Wei et al., 2019, Gómez-Marín et al., 2025], drum loop synthesis [Alain et al., 2020, Lattner and Grachten, 2019], and drum sample modeling [Nistal Hurlé et al., 2020, Lavault et al., 2022]. Whereas those efforts focus on symbolic representations or isolated sounds, our approach seeks to translate real world sound gestures into coherent, full drumkit audio realizations.

3.4 Dataset

MusDB18 Dataset. The MusDB18 dataset [Rafii et al., 2017] contains 150 professionally produced stereo music tracks spanning a wide range of genres, totaling roughly 10 hours of audio. Each track is distributed into isolated stems for *drums*, *bass*, *vocals*, and *other*, along with the full mixture. The dataset provides a standardized split into 100 tracks for training and 50 tracks for testing. In this work, we make use of the official train split for model training and the test split for evaluation.

3.4.1 Rhythm Representation

A core challenge in mapping vocal or gestural rhythms (such as beatboxing or tapping) onto drum sounds lies in disentangling timbral from rhythmic information. The timbre should be dictated exclusively by the timbre prompt, while the rhythm prompt provides the temporal structure. If the rhythm representation unintentionally encodes timbral details, the model risks ignoring the timbre prompt. Conversely, if the rhythm descriptors differ too drastically between human vocalizations and actual drum signals, transferring gestural patterns into convincing drum realizations becomes unreliable.

One simplistic choice for rhythm features is the use of a one channel groove representation (as explored in GrooVAE [Gillick et al., 2019, Haki et al., 2022]), which primarily reflects onset timing. While such a curve can highlight rhythmic accents, it cannot differentiate the functional roles of percussion instruments: for instance, kicks and snares will collapse into the same channel, thereby masking their distinct rhythmic functions [Haki et al., 2023a]. At the other extreme, employing a high resolution spectrogram risks the opposite issue: it captures too much spec-

tral detail, leaking timbre specific cues into the rhythm stream. In addition, this mismatch between how drums and vocal sounds appear in spectrogram space can hinder generalization during inference.

To strike a balance, TRIA introduces a two-band spectrogram feature. Starting from an 80-bin mel spectrogram, the frequency axis is divided adaptively such that low and high-frequency regions each carry comparable energy. Within each band, mel bins are summed to form a compact two dimensional time sequence describing rhythmic energy in low vs. high regions. These sequences are normalized per band, squashed into the $[0, 1]$ range using a sigmoid, and then discretized into 17 quantization levels $(0, 1/17, 2/17, \dots, 1)$. This scheme captures rhythmic structure without leaking timbral information, while still preserving distinctions between different percussive gestures.

This dual band representation also draws inspiration from symbolic rhythm models that reduce patterns into alternating high-low states, which have been shown to effectively capture structural aspects of rhythm [Haki et al., 2023a, Lartillot and Bruford, 2021]. By extending this abstraction to the audio domain, TRIA offers a lightweight but musically meaningful conditioning signal for drum generation.

TRIA features are computed with a hop size of 1024 samples. This produces more frames than required for the latent sequence. To synchronize conditioning features with the diffusion model, the TRIA feature sequence is interpolated to exactly align with the diffusion timesteps, ensuring that each generated latent token is guided by a temporally corresponding rhythmic feature. This alignment is crucial for maintaining precise rhythmic control throughout the generative process.

3.4.2 TRIA Feature Extraction

We denote the rhythm prompt audio as $x(t)$, where t indexes time. The TRIA feature extraction pipeline consists of the following steps:

1. Mel-Spectrogram First, we compute an 80-bin mel-spectrogram $S \in \mathbb{R}^{80 \times T}$ with hop size 1024 samples:

$$S = \text{MelSpec}(x(t)), \quad S_{b,\tau} \geq 0,$$

where $b = 1, \dots, 80$ indexes mel bins, and $\tau = 1, \dots, T$ indexes frames.

2. Adaptive Band Splitting We compute the cumulative energy distribution across mel bins:

$$E(b) = \sum_{\tau=1}^T S_{b,\tau}, \quad E_{\text{tot}} = \sum_{b=1}^{80} E(b).$$

The splitting frequency index b^* is chosen such that

$$\sum_{b=1}^{b^*} E(b) \approx \frac{1}{2} E_{\text{tot}}.$$

This partitions the spectrogram into a *low-band* and a *high-band* representation.

3. Band Summation The band energies are aggregated frame wise:

$$L_\tau = \sum_{b=1}^{b^*} S_{b,\tau}, \quad H_\tau = \sum_{b=b^*+1}^{80} S_{b,\tau}.$$

4. Standardization and Sigmoid Compression Each band is standardized and passed through a sigmoid nonlinearity:

$$\tilde{L}_\tau = \sigma\left(\frac{L_\tau - \mu_L}{\sigma_L}\right), \quad \tilde{H}_\tau = \sigma\left(\frac{H_\tau - \mu_H}{\sigma_H}\right),$$

where μ_L, σ_L and μ_H, σ_H are the mean and standard deviation of L_τ and H_τ across time, and $\sigma(z) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-z}}$ is the sigmoid.

5. Quantization Finally, values are discretized to $Q = 17$ bins:

$$Q(v) = \frac{1}{Q-1} \cdot \text{round}((Q-1) \cdot v), \quad v \in [0, 1].$$

Thus the final TRIA feature sequence is

$$\text{TRIA}(\tau) = (Q(\tilde{L}_\tau), Q(\tilde{H}_\tau)).$$

Algorithm 1 TRIA Feature Extraction

Require: Rhythm prompt audio $x(t)$

Ensure: TRIA features $\{(\tilde{L}_\tau, \tilde{H}_\tau)\}_{\tau=1}^T$

- 1: $S \leftarrow \text{MelSpectrogram}(x(t), \text{bins} = 80, \text{hop} = 1024)$
 - 2: $E(b) \leftarrow \sum_\tau S_{b,\tau}$ for $b = 1, \dots, 80$
 - 3: Find b^* such that $\sum_{b=1}^{b^*} E(b) \approx \frac{1}{2} \sum_{b=1}^{80} E(b)$
 - 4: **for** $\tau = 1$ to T **do**
 - 5: $L_\tau \leftarrow \sum_{b=1}^{b^*} S_{b,\tau}$
 - 6: $H_\tau \leftarrow \sum_{b=b^*+1}^{80} S_{b,\tau}$
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: Standardize $\{L_\tau\}$ and $\{H_\tau\}$ to zero mean, unit variance
 - 9: Apply sigmoid: $\tilde{L}_\tau = \sigma(L_\tau)$, $\tilde{H}_\tau = \sigma(H_\tau)$
 - 10: Quantize each value to $Q = 17$ levels in $[0, 1]$
 - 11: **return** TRIA features $\{(\tilde{L}_\tau, \tilde{H}_\tau)\}_{\tau=1}^T$
-

3.5 Method

3.5.1 Architecture

Our system builds on the Stable Audio Open (SAO) framework [Evans et al., 2025], specifically the base variant introduced in [Novack et al., 2025], and adapts it into a more efficient generative model for drum synthesis. The model is designed to generate variable length stereo audio signals (up to approximately 11.9 seconds) at a sampling rate of 44.1 kHz. Unlike symbolic approaches, this model operates directly in the audio domain, synthesizing realistic waveforms while retaining precise control over timing.

At its core, the architecture follows a latent generative modeling paradigm. First, input audio waveforms are encoded into a compressed representation using a 156M-parameter pretrained autoencoder provided by SAO. This encoder maps raw waveforms into a 64 channel latent space with a temporal resolution of 21.5 Hz, effectively capturing perceptually salient features while discarding redundancies. Operating in this low rate latent space substantially reduces the computational burden of downstream generative modeling, while preserving audio fidelity at reconstruction.

For conditioning, we adopt a 109M-parameter T5-based text encoder, which provides semantically rich embeddings for textual prompts. Although our system does not primarily rely on text for generation, this component ensures compatibility with broader SAO pipelines and enables flexible conditioning in future extensions (e.g., text-guided rhythm or timbre).

The generative backbone is a Diffusion Transformer (DiT) [Evans et al., 2024] trained to operate in the latent domain, as seen in Figure 7. Following the SAO design, the DiT is first pretrained as a rectified flow model, which stabilizes learning and accelerates convergence by reframing diffusion as an approximate flow matching task. During inference, the DiT gradually refines samples in latent space before they are decoded back into high fidelity stereo waveforms by the SAO decoder.

Taken together, this design strikes a balance between generative capacity and practical efficiency, making it feasible to train and deploy the model on relatively modest hardware resources while still achieving high quality audio synthesis.

3.5.2 Conditioning Mechanisms

Conditioning plays a central role in guiding the generative process of our model. In the original Stable Audio Open (SAO) architecture, the Diffusion Transformer (DiT) is conditioned on three primary signals: text embeddings (providing language based control), timing embeddings (enabling variable length generation), and timestep embeddings (indicating the current stage of the diffusion process). Text conditioning is obtained from a pretrained T5-base encoder, while timing and timestep conditioning are injected via sinusoidal embeddings, introduced either through cross attention or

Figure 7: Architecture of the diffusion transformer (DiT). Cross attention includes text and rhythm conditioning. Prepend conditioning includes timbre conditioning and also the signal conditioning on the current timestep of the diffusion process.

prepend strategies.

In contrast, our system departs significantly from this setup. While the text conditioning branch is retained for architectural compatibility, it is not used during training, effectively rendering text input null in our framework. Similarly, we remove explicit timing control, as our focus is on fine grained rhythmic conditioning derived directly from audio gestures, rather than duration metadata. The only conditioning mechanism we preserve unchanged from SAO is the use of timestep embeddings, which remain fundamental to diffusion based generation.

Our design introduces two complementary conditioning mechanisms tailored specifically for drum synthesis.

(1) Rhythm Conditioning via TRIA Features (Sketch2Sound inspired).

To represent temporal rhythmic structure, we adapt the Sketch2Sound paradigm [García et al., 2025], which conditions generation on frame level control signals. Whereas the original design employs descriptors such as loudness, brightness, and pitch, we instead make use of TRIA features [O’Reilly et al.], extracted directly from rhythmic input sources (e.g., beatboxing or tapping). TRIA encodes each frame into a dual-band representation of low and high-frequency rhythmic energy, providing a compact yet expressive proxy for rhythmic intent. To enable alignment with the audio generation process, we interpolate the temporal resolution of TRIA frames to match the latent sequence output by the SAO autoencoder, ensuring a strict framewise correspondence. These control signals are projected into the latent dimensionality of the diffusion model and added elementwise to the latent representation before the DiT forward pass. This additive conditioning strategy enables the model to follow rhythmic gestures in a continuous, time varying fashion, while retaining flexibility for expressive generation during inference.

(2) Timbre Conditioning via Latent Overwrite. Timbre control is achieved through a direct latent overwriting mechanism. Given a timbre prompt (a reference drum recording), we pass the audio through the SAO autoencoder to obtain latent embeddings that capture the target drumkit’s timbral characteristics. During training, a randomly selected prefix of the diffusion latent sequence (between 20 - 50%) is overwritten with the corresponding segment from the timbre latent. A binary mask is constructed to mark the overwritten positions, ensuring that no reconstruction loss is computed over these regions. This procedure constitutes a form of explicit latent conditioning, which circumvents the complexity of concatenation based methods, while robustly enforcing inheritance of timbral properties from the reference prompt.

By combining these two conditioning pathways, TRIA-based additive rhythm control and latent overwrite timbre conditioning, our model learns to disentangle rhythmic structure from timbral style, enabling flexible generation of drum performances from simple sound gestures. Importantly, unlike transcription based approaches, this framework does not rely on symbolic intermediates, but rather leverages self-supervised conditioning directly in the audio domain.

3.5.3 Pretrained Autoencoder for Audio Latents

At the core of the latent generative framework lies a pretrained autoencoder, provided by SAO, which maps raw waveforms into a perceptually meaningful and temporally compressed representation. The encoder consists of five convolutional blocks, each performing strided convolutions for downsampling while simultaneously expanding the number of channels. Prior to each downsampling stage, the model applies a sequence of residual layers with dilated convolutions and Snake activations [Ziyin et al., 2020], which improve the representation of oscillatory signals and fine temporal structures. Figure 8 illustrates the architecture of the autoencoder.

The bottleneck of the autoencoder is parameterized as a variational latent space with dimensionality 64, enabling stochastic sampling and regularization of the latent manifold. The decoder mirrors the encoder in structure, employing transposed strided convolutions to progressively upsample while reducing the channel dimension. This architecture yields a 64-channel latent representation operating at a temporal resolution of 21.5 Hz.

Operating in this low rate latent space substantially reduces the computational burden of downstream generative modeling, while preserving high-quality reconstructions. The pretrained autoencoder comprises approximately 156 million parameters and is frozen during all subsequent training stages in our system.

Figure 8: Architecture of the autoencoder used for latent representation learning. The encoder maps raw audio waveforms to a compressed latent space, while the decoder reconstructs the audio from this latent representation.

3.5.4 Diffusion Transformer Architecture for Latent Diffusion (Flow) Modeling

The generative backbone of the model is a Diffusion Transformer (DiT) [Evans et al., 2024], which extends the transformer paradigm to the diffusion setting. At its core, the DiT is composed of stacked transformer blocks, each containing serially connected self attention and gated multi layer perceptrons (MLPs), with residual skip connections around each sublayer. Bias-less layer normalization is applied before both the attention and MLP components, stabilizing training and improving generalization. Rotary positional embeddings [Su et al., 2023] are applied to half of the attention keys and queries, providing relative position encoding.

To incorporate conditioning, each block includes a cross attention mechanism. Conditioning signals include text, timing, and diffusion timesteps. Text features are extracted via a pretrained T5-base encoder [Raffel et al., 2023], and timestep embeddings follow sinusoidal encodings [Ho et al., 2020]. Conditioning signals are introduced through a combination of cross attention and prepended embeddings, with text applied in cross attention, and timestep prepended to the input sequence.

Linear mappings are applied both at the input and output of the transformer to project between the autoencoder latent space and the transformer’s embedding dimension. For efficiency, block wise attention [Dao et al., 2022] and gradient checkpointing [Chen et al., 2016] are employed, reducing memory and compute requirements.

The specific variant adopted here builds on the SAO framework [Evans et al., 2025], but with architectural modifications to improve efficiency while retaining generation quality. The DiT operates on the 64-channel latent representations produced by the pretrained autoencoder, and is conditioned on 109M-parameter T5 embeddings [Raffel et al., 2023]. Compared to the original 1.06B-parameter DiT, the model reduces the embedding dimension from 1536 to 1024, and the depth from 24 to 16 layers, while additionally incorporating QK-LayerNorm [Henry et al., 2020] and removing the “seconds start” embedding. These adjustments reduce the parameter count to 340M while maintaining synthesis quality and improving training stability. During inference, the base DiT is compiled using `torch.compile`, yielding further gains in runtime efficiency.

3.5.5 Inference

At inference time, our system requires two inputs: a timbre prompt in the form of a short drum recording, and a rhythm prompt provided as a sound gesture (e.g., a tapping pattern, beatboxing, or another percussive input). The timbre prompt is first passed through the Stable Audio autoencoder to obtain its latent representation, which we use to initialize the prefix of the generation buffer. This prefix is left unmasked and remains fixed throughout the process, ensuring that the timbral identity of the final output faithfully matches the given recording. The remaining portion of the buffer, corresponding in length to the rhythm prompt, is fully masked and designated as the suffix to be generated. Rhythm features are then computed from the rhythm prompt and temporally aligned to this masked suffix, providing the model with explicit rhythmic conditioning.

Generation proceeds through an iterative denoising procedure based on Euler sampling, carried out over 50 discrete steps. At each step, the model progressively refines the masked suffix latents, gradually transforming them from noise into coherent representations consistent with the provided rhythm. After every denoising update, the original timbre prefix is reinserted into the buffer before continuing to the next step. This replacement step is crucial: without it, the model could inadvertently alter the timbral prompt during sampling, drifting away from the intended drum identity. By continually restoring the prefix, we guarantee that the model is always conditioned on the correct timbre context while generating the suffix.

The result is a sequence of latents in which the suffix is coherently “filled in” using both sources of conditioning: timbral characteristics from the prefix and rhythmic structure from the computed TRIA features. The tradeoff between strict adherence to conditioning and creative variability is controlled by classifier-free guidance (CFG). In our implementation, the CFG scale can be adjusted to emphasize either

timbre or rhythm conditioning, or to allow for looser interpretations that produce more diverse outputs. To make this process accessible to end users, we developed a Gradio interface in which the number of sampling steps and the CFG scale are exposed as adjustable parameters. This allows musicians and producers to experiment with different configurations, from faithful reconstructions to more imaginative generations.

3.5.6 Training Objective and Conditioning

For training, we follow the flow matching framework [Lipman et al., 2023], where noise is applied to the encoded audio latents and the model is trained to denoise them. Let $\mathbf{x}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{F \times D}$ denote the encoded audio latents of dimension D with $F = 256$ latent frames. We sample a timestep $\tau \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1)$ and construct noisy latents by convex combination with Gaussian noise:

$$\mathbf{x}_\tau = (1 - \tau)\mathbf{x}_0 + \tau\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \quad \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{I}). \quad (3.1)$$

The model is trained to predict \mathbf{x}_0 from \mathbf{x}_τ using the rectified flow objective, i.e.,

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{RF}} = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_0, \boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \tau} \left[\left\| \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0(\mathbf{x}_\tau, \tau, \mathbf{c}) - \mathbf{x}_0 \right\|_2^2 \right], \quad (3.2)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0(\cdot)$ denotes the model prediction and \mathbf{c} are conditioning signals. Note that loss is computed only over the suffix portion of latents (outside the timbre prefix span).

Training At each iteration, we begin by sampling a drum recording from the MusDB training set and extracting a random 11.89 second segment of the isolated drum track. This segment is passed through the pretrained Stable Audio autoencoder (SAO) to obtain a sequence of continuous latents, which serve as the reconstruction target. Flow matching noise is then applied to the latent sequence, and the model is trained using the rectified flow objective, with mean squared error (MSE) computed between predicted and target latents [Chang et al., 2022].

To condition generation, we incorporate both timbre and rhythm information in complementary ways. To avoid redundant information, rhythm features are zeroed out in the prefix region so that the model relies solely on timbre latents there, while in the suffix region the model must reconstruct the target latents by combining timbre information from the prefix with rhythmic cues from TRIA.

To improve generalization to rhythm prompts from diverse sources such as tapping, beatboxing, or low quality recordings, we apply a set of augmentations to audio when computing rhythm features. These include additive Gaussian noise, pitch shifting, and high or low-pass filtering. Importantly, these augmentations are never applied to the audio used for encoding target latents, ensuring that the model always learns to predict clean latents while adapting to noisy or degraded rhythm conditioning.

Finally, we employ classifier-free guidance (CFG) [Ho and Salimans, 2022] dropout

to control the degree of adherence to conditioning. During training, rhythm conditioning is independently disabled in 10% of iterations by replacing their embeddings with null prompts, enabling the model to learn both conditional and unconditional mappings. At inference time, we apply CFG with a scale of 2, interpolating between unconditional and conditional predictions to balance timbre prompt adherence with rhythm prompt adherence.

3.6 Experiments and Evaluation

We developed the system through a series of experimental refinements:

Initial model with no CFG control This was our first attempt at implementing the core architecture and training procedure. Even though the loss went down, the generated samples were of low quality and did not adhere well to either timbre or rhythm prompts. There was no mechanism to balance the two conditioning sources, leading to outputs that were often muddled or incoherent.

Incorporation of classifier-free guidance (CFGScale) Adding CFG improved our ability to control the influence of timbre and rhythm prompts. At very high values of CFG scale (5-7), the model produced outputs that started to adhere to the rhythm prompt, but the timbre was often lost or distorted at high CFG scales. One notable observation was that the model struggled to maintain a consistent timbral identity when heavily conditioned on rhythm.

Switching controls projection from latent space to DiT embedding space (DiTProj) Instead of adding our conditioning signals directly in the latent space, we introduced linear projections to map both the TRIA features and the timbre latents into the DiT’s embedding space. This change significantly improved the model’s ability to integrate conditioning information, leading to better adherence to both prompts. The outputs became more coherent, with clearer rhythmic structures and more faithful timbral characteristics, even at normal CFG scales.

Data augmentations to enhance generalization to real world gestures (DataAug) To ensure the model could handle a variety of rhythm prompts, we applied augmentations such as noise addition, pitch shifting, and filtering when computing TRIA features. This step was crucial for improving robustness, as it exposed the model to a wider range of rhythmic inputs during training. The augmented training led to better performance on unseen rhythm prompts, particularly those derived from beatboxing or tapping.

We evaluate the model from each stage on the MusDB test set to assess its performance. Evaluation focuses on two key aspects: Rhythm Prompt Adherence and Timbre Prompt Adherence.

3.6.1 Rhythm Prompt Adherence

To assess how well our models preserve rhythmic information from the prompt, we adopt an automatic drum transcription based evaluation, on the held out test split of MusDB (50 tracks), which was not used for training. For each track, we consider the ground truth drum stem as a reference and generate corresponding drum outputs from our system.

Both the ground truth stems and the model outputs are transcribed using the pre-trained Frame-RNN drum transcription model [Zehren et al., 2023], yielding symbolic onset sequences for kick, snare, and hi-hat. We measure the correspondence between the two transcriptions using the onset F1 score at 30ms tolerance, as is standard practice in drum transcription evaluation [Vogl et al., 2017, Heydari et al., 2021]. Higher F1 values indicate closer alignment between the temporal placement of drum hits in the reference stem and the generated output.

Model	CFG	F1 Kick	F1 Snare	F1 HiHats
CFGScale	1	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3	0.05	0.01	0.02
DiTProj	1	0.25	0.30	0.00
	2	0.43	0.46	0.16
	3	0.43	0.52	0.24
DataAug	1	0.59	0.43	0.15
	2	0.82	0.65	0.38
	3	0.84	0.66	0.37

Table 4: Channelwise F1 scores for each model across CFG scales.

3.6.2 Timbre Prompt Adherence

To evaluate timbre preservation, we again draw on the MusDB test set drum stems as source material. For each evaluation instance, we supply the model with a timbre prompt (a drum stem excerpt) and a rhythm prompt. The goal is to determine whether the generated output retains the spectral and textural qualities of the timbre prompt, while remaining unaffected by the rhythm prompt in terms of timbral content.

We quantify timbre similarity using feature based measures computed on short time spectral representations. Specifically, we compare the 80 dimensional temporally averaged MFCC representations of the generated audio and timbre prompt via cosine similarity. A higher similarity indicates stronger timbral adherence.

Model	CFG 1	CFG 2	CFG 3
DiTProj	0.94	0.95	0.96
DataAug	0.94	0.96	0.98

Table 5: Mean timbre similarity for each model across CFG scales.

3.7 Discussion

Tables 4 and 5 summarize the results of our evaluations. Rhythm prompt adherence, as measured by onset F1 scores, shows a clear progression across model variants. The initial CFGScale model exhibits minimal rhythmic fidelity, with F1 scores near zero across all channels. The DiTProj variant demonstrates substantial improvements, particularly at higher CFG scales, indicating that projection space modifications significantly enhance the model’s ability to follow rhythmic cues. The DataAug model achieves the highest F1 scores, with values exceeding 0.8 for kick and 0.65 for snare at CFG2. Hi-hat F1 scores remain lower overall, reflecting the inherent difficulty of accurately capturing high frequency, rapid percussion elements. Timbre similarity remains consistently high across all models, with mean cosine similarities above 0.94. It must be noted that timbre evaluations here are restricted to drum sounds present in the MusDB dataset, in future work we aim to quantify timbre generalization to out of distribution drum sounds.

Nevertheless, our listening tests also surfaced important limitations. While classifier-free guidance (CFG) and rhythm augmentations improved performance, timbre generalization is imperfect, particularly for rare drum sounds or heavily processed stems in the MusDB dataset. Similarly, transcription based evaluation introduces its own sources of error, as the accuracy of onset detection directly impacts rhythm adherence scores. Evaluation protocols that integrate perceptual listening tests or learned embeddings more closely aligned with timbre may yield more reliable assessments.

Beyond the scope of quantitative metrics, qualitative experiments showed that the system can recombine rhythmic and timbral cues in musically compelling ways, often producing plausible and stylistically coherent drum tracks. This validates our broader vision of generative rhythm timbre transfer: enabling musicians to impose a desired groove structure onto a chosen drum sound, much like a producer layering the feel of one drummer with the kit of another. However, further work is needed to refine the model’s ability to handle extreme or out of distribution inputs, as well as to explore user interfaces that facilitate intuitive control over the generation process.

3.8 Conclusion and Future Work

Several avenues emerge for future work. First, more robust timbre similarity measures, potentially based on pretrained audio embeddings, could complement MFCC cosine metrics and capture perceptual qualities beyond spectral energy. Second, user centric evaluation will be critical: perceptual studies with musicians and pro-

ducers could reveal how controllable and musically useful such systems truly are. Finally, extending this framework beyond drum synthesis toward other instrument classes may generalize the prefix suffix conditioning paradigm as a powerful tool for controllable audio generation.

Chapter 4

Model Deployment for End Users

While the core of this thesis has focused on the design, training, and evaluation of machine learning models for modeling expressive rhythms, an equally important contribution lies in the exporting and deployment of these models into usable tools. Making research artifacts available to musicians and practitioners outside the lab is essential to bridging the gap between academic research and artistic practice.

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, we describe the process of exporting and deploying the models developed in the two independent works presented in this thesis: (1) *Learning Microrhythm in Uruguayan Candombe using Transformers*, and (2) *GotThatFlow: Flow-based Beatbox-to-Rhythm Generation*. For both projects, we detail the export formats used, the deployment contexts (plugins and demos), and the reception or current status of these deployments.

4.2 Learning Microrhythm in Uruguayan Candombe using Transformers

4.2.1 Exporting via TorchScript

The trained Transformer model for microrhythm generation was exported using TorchScript, a serialization format provided by PyTorch that allows models to be run independently of Python. TorchScript enables integration into C++ environments and plugin frameworks, which is crucial for deployment in digital audio workstations (DAWs).

Unlike ONNX or other intermediate representations, TorchScript provides a relatively seamless path for PyTorch-trained models to be used in C++ without introducing third-party runtime dependencies. This reduces deployment friction and

Figure 9: Interface of the Candombe VST plugin. The plugin processes incoming MIDI events and applies microrhythmic transformations based on the learned Candombe grooves.

improves stability within DAW environments.

The PyTorch model was traced using `torch.jit.trace` and subsequently saved as a TorchScript module. The exported module was validated against the Python version to ensure parity of results.

4.2.2 Wrapping in NeuralMidiFX VST

To make the model accessible to musicians, the TorchScript model was integrated into the NeuralMidiFX [Haki et al., 2023b] VST wrapper. This wrapper provides a framework for embedding neural models inside VST plugins. Within this setup, the plugin accepts incoming MIDI input and outputs rhythmically transformed MIDI events, applying microrhythmic deviations learned from Candombe performances. The plugin interface is shown in Figure 9.

Musicians can load the plugin in their preferred DAW (Ableton Live, Logic Pro, etc.) and directly enrich MIDI sequences with authentic Candombe grooves.

Figure 10: Integration of the Candombe VST plugin within the MTG Toolbox environment. This setup allows users to easily install and utilize the plugin alongside other MTG Toolbox applications

4.2.3 Real-World Deployment

The plugin is released publicly on Github ¹ and has been adopted by musicians worldwide. The plugin will also be accessible in an easy to install format at the MTG Toolbox page ², as seen in Figure 10. Early feedback from users has been positive, with the plugin successfully capturing the feel of the genre.

A demo paper describing this plugin was published at the Late-Breaking Demo session of ISMIR 2024 conference, and a talk presenting the plugin was delivered at the ADCx 2025 India conference.

4.3 GotThatFlow: Flow-based Beatbox-to-Rhythm Generation

4.3.1 ONNX Export

The beatbox-to-rhythm generation model, adapted from the Stable Audio Open Small backbone, was designed with deployment efficiency in mind. To enable fast inference, the model was exported to ONNX (Open Neural Network Exchange) format.

ONNX offers broad compatibility across frameworks and is optimized for deployment scenarios, including real-time inference with ONNX Runtime. Compared to TorchScript, ONNX provides more flexibility for hardware acceleration (e.g., GPU, CPU, and mobile devices).

¹<https://github.com/dhunstack/candombe-groove-vst>

²<http://mtg-toolbox.github.io/ready-to-use-apps/candombe-vst>

4.3.2 Gradio Demo Deployment

To provide an accessible entry point for experimentation, a Gradio demo of the model was deployed. This demo allows users to upload a beatbox recording and receive drums output in real time via a web interface.

Figure 11: Deployment of the GotThatFlow model as a Gradio web demo. Users can upload beatbox audio and receive generated drum patterns in real time.

The demo demonstrates that the model can run faster than real time, validating its feasibility for live applications. Non-technical users can interact with the model without installing dependencies or compiling plugins.

4.3.3 Toward a VST Plugin

While the Gradio demo provides immediate accessibility, the long-term goal is to wrap the ONNX model in a plugin format (e.g., VST/AU) using ONNX Runtime, enabling integration into DAWs similar to the microrhythm plugin. Once finalized, the plugin will allow live beatbox-to-rhythm transformation inside DAWs, opening new creative workflows for producers and performers.

While model accuracy and novelty are essential within the academic context, accessibility and usability are equally critical for adoption by musicians. The deployment efforts described here represent initial steps toward making these models practical tools for music creation.

4.4 Conclusion

In this chapter, we presented the implementation and deployment aspects of our system, focusing on the process of exporting models to TorchScript and ONNX formats, validating their performance, and integrating them into practical tools such as a VST plugin and a lightweight Gradio interface. These efforts address the practical goals of our research: making rhythm generation models usable outside of purely academic contexts and accessible to a broader community of musicians.

From a technical perspective, the successful export and validation of the models demonstrates that advanced generative architectures can be efficiently serialized and executed on local hardware. This contributes toward our broader aim of reducing reliance on cloud-based infrastructure, thus lowering barriers to access while ensuring privacy and enabling spontaneous, real-time interaction. The GitHub release, early adoption by musicians, and anecdotal validation from percussionists highlight the promise of such tools in bridging the gap between research prototypes and practical creative applications. From a creative perspective, the plugins illustrate how generative models can be embedded into familiar music production environments, allowing performers and producers to experiment with rhythms interactively.

More broadly, these results reinforce the motivations set out in the introduction. By enabling rhythm generation systems that are both expressive and accessible, this work takes a step toward bridging the gap between human nuance and machine creativity. The technical advances in deployment point to a future where generative music systems are not just tools for producing sounds, but companions in the creative process. Ultimately, this aligns with the overarching goal of this thesis: to design models and interfaces that make human-machine collaboration in music both natural and fun.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

This thesis has explored the generation of expressive percussion music through two complementary approaches: symbolic microrhythm modeling and audio-domain drums synthesis. Across both projects, the overarching goal has been to bridge the gap between human rhythmic expressivity and machine-generated outputs, providing models that can capture nuanced temporal structures while remaining accessible for creative practice.

5.1 Summary of Contributions

5.1.1 Learning Microrhythm in Uruguayan Candombe

In the symbolic domain, we developed a Transformer-based framework to learn the intricate microtiming patterns characteristic of Uruguayan Candombe drumming. By analyzing onset deviations and temporal dynamics in a structured HVO representation, the model captures subtle rhythmic variations that define the style. Experimental evaluation demonstrated that the system successfully reproduces these microtiming patterns, in both quantitative validation and qualitative evidence from user feedback. Beyond the technical achievement, this work supports cultural preservation and offers musicians a tool for integrating Candombe grooves into their compositions.

5.1.2 GotThatFlow: Flow-based Beatbox-to-Rhythm Generation

In the audio domain, we introduced a flow-based latent diffusion model capable of transforming arbitrary sound gestures into coherent drum rhythms. Through the combination of TRIA feature conditioning and latent timbre overwrite, the model disentangles rhythmic structure from timbral content, allowing flexible rhythm conditioning from diverse input sources. Evaluations confirm adherence to rhythm prompts, and real-time inference via a Gradio demo demonstrates the potential

for interactive creative applications. This work uses state of the art methods for conditioned audio generation while providing a tangible platform for musicians to experiment with drums generation in real time on local machines.

5.2 Practical Impact and Deployment

A key focus throughout the thesis has been translating research prototypes into usable tools. The Candombe microtiming model was successfully deployed as a TorchScript-based VST plugin, receiving positive feedback from musicians and reaching a global audience. GotThatFlow has been validated via a Gradio interface, with ongoing efforts to create a fully integrated plugin for DAW use. These deployment efforts are important for usability and accessibility alongside model performance, ensuring that the research can meaningfully impact musical practice.

5.3 Broader Perspectives and Future Directions

Both projects contribute to the broader understanding of generative percussion modeling, illustrating how symbolic and audio-domain approaches can complement each other. Future work may include: enhancing temporal flexibility in symbolic models, extending audio-domain systems to handle more complex multi-instrument scenarios, and investigating culturally-informed rhythm modeling beyond the datasets considered here.

5.4 Closing Remarks

Taken together, the contributions of this thesis advance the state of generative percussion modeling by combining rigorous technical methods with practical, user-facing applications. In 1993, Professor Jeffrey Bilmes ended his seminal thesis [Bilmes, 1993] with the following words:

“The main goal of this thesis was to represent and reproduce expressive timing in percussive musical rhythm - that is, to design algorithms that computers can use to produce expressive sounding rhythmic phrases. I believe I have been successful in this endeavor and have begun to quantitatively describe one of the many elusive human behaviors. Music is one of the most important means of expression, and rhythm is probably the most important means of attaining musical expression. We have herein begun to produce expressive sounding rhythmic phrases using a computer”

Nearly three decades later, this thesis continues in that spirit, pushing the boundaries of what machines can achieve in the realm of expressive percussion music. By combining advances in deep learning with a deep appreciation for musical nuance, we have taken meaningful steps toward realizing that vision. The journey is far from

over, but the foundations laid here provide a solid platform for future exploration and innovation in generative music technology.

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